

RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Event: Research Data Management for NFDI Consortia

This hybrid event is designed for both beginners and experienced professionals in Research Data Management (RDM) who currently provide — or plan to provide — generic and/or discipline-specific training.

Organized by [RDMTraining4NFDI](#) and enriched with insights from experienced external trainers, the program offers a dynamic mix of learning formats. Where possible, parallel sessions will be tailored to different experience levels. Participants will have the flexibility to register for one, several, or all event formats, depending on their interests and availability.

Our goals:

- Deliver practical, focused RDM guidance within a condensed time frame.
- Strengthen participants' training skills (including didactics) and data management expertise.
- Foster the exchange of best practices within the RDM community.
- Experiment with and evaluate diverse training formats.

Registration deadline: 6 October 2025

Please note: you may not receive an automated confirmation upon registering. However, you will receive a follow-up email with detailed information in mid-September, or — for later registrations — by the registration deadline at the latest.

Dates and Times

28–29 October 2025 — Lunch-To-Lunch In-Person Kick-off
Event (ca. 8 teaching hours)

Trainer: Antje Manske (GESIS)

Topic: Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management

Research Data Management (RDM) professionals – such as data stewards, research data managers, and data curators – play a key role in realizing the goals of FAIR data and Open Science. To lead impactful RDM projects and inspire better data practices, they need the skills and strategies to shape and execute strategies and to manage change.

This interactive lunch-to-lunch course equips RDM professionals with hands-on tools, methods, and templates that can be applied right away.

What Will You Learn?

This course is for RDM professional who want to:

- Identify and manage their stakeholders
- Clearly communicate their role and services to foster collaboration and adoption

- Set meaningful strategic goals in collaboration with stakeholders and translate these into actionable plans
- Prioritize daily responsibilities to gain more time for strategic initiatives
- Evaluate the impact of planned changes and manage change effectively
- Build resilience in handling different responses to change
- By the end of this course, participants will be ready to build stronger partnerships and lead change with more confidence.

This course is adapted from “Agents of Change”: Manske, A., & Zänkert, S. (2024, November 26). Agents of Change - Skills & Strategies for RDM Professionals. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14221846>

Venue

SR-Marie-Curie-R413
ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences
Gleueler Strasse 60, 50931 Cologne, Germany

Costs

- **Accommodation:** participants are responsible for booking their own hotel. RDMTraining4NFDI will reimburse accommodation costs up to €80 per night. If no reasonably close option is available within this limit, reimbursement of up to €100–€120 per night may be granted with justification.
- **Catering:** refreshments and meals will be provided during the day. An evening meal will be covered (up to €20). Please note: alcoholic beverages cannot be financed from Base4NFDI project funds.
- **Transport:** transport costs will be reimbursed in accordance with the North Rhine-Westphalia Travel Expenses Act.

Note: participants will need to self-finance travel costs upfront and subsequently submit the ZB MED cash expense form for reimbursement. The cash expense form will be provided after the event.

3–21 November 2025 – Interactive Workshop Series (Online via Zoom, ca. 18 teaching hours)

Schedule: Tuesdays & Thursdays, 09:00–12:00

- 04 Nov — Foundations of RDM (beginners)
- 06 Nov — Practical Data Protection in Research
- 11 Nov — Python (beginners)
- 13 Nov — Git (parallel sessions for beginners and advanced)
- 18 Nov — Introduction to Galaxy Training!
- 20 Nov — Didactics & Motivation

If you are unable to attend all online sessions, please inform us in advance.

3–21 November 2025 – Self-Learning Modules (ca. 14 teaching hours)

- [Foundations of RDM](#) (train-the-trainer)
- [Open Science](#)

- [Python](#) (advanced)
- [Git](#) (beginners)
- [Data Management Plans](#) (train-the-trainer)
- [Data Sharing](#)

Note: this is a provisional schedule and subject to change. Further details regarding the trainers and the self-learning materials will be provided in a later email.

24 November – 5 December 2025 – Asynchronous Homework

Adapt the material to your discipline and/or review existing discipline-specific resources.

11 December 2025 — Wrap-Up Event (Online via Zoom)

Final presentations of participant results.

Good to Know

All participants who complete the program (or individual modules) will receive a certificate of attendance.

Organizer

The following RDMTraining4NFDI institutions will lead the organisation, moderation, and delivery of selected workshops:

- ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences
- TH Köln – University of Applied Sciences

Contact

First name, last name: [name@organization.de](mailto:organization.de)

Registration Form

1. First and last names [Open answer]
2. Email address [Open answer]
3. Institution [Open answer]
4. NFDI consortia (select all that apply)
 - BERD@NFDI
 - FAIRagro
 - KonsortSWD
 - MaRDI
 - NFDI4Biodiversity
 - NFDI4BiolImage
 - NFDI4Cat
 - NFDI4Chem
 - NFDI4Memory
 - NFDI4Microbiota
 - Other

5. Research area [Open answer]
6. Career stage (select all that apply)
 - Ph.D. candidate
 - Postdoctoral researcher
 - Junior professor
 - Professor
 - Director of an institute
 - RDM professional
 - Data steward
 - Data librarian
 - Trainer
 - Developer
 - Other
7. Which parts of the RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Event would you like to attend?
 - All modules
 - Kick-off event in Cologne (28-29 October 2025)
 - Online workshop series (3-21 November 2025)
 - Self-learning modules (November 2025)
 - Asynchronous homework (24 November - 5 December 2025)
 - Online wrap-up event (11 December 2025)
8. Do you have any dietary requirements? (select all that apply)
 - Lactose intolerance
 - Gluten intolerance or sensitivity
 - Vegetarianism
 - Veganism
 - Wheat allergy
 - Nut allergy
 - Fish and seafood allergy
 - Egg allergy
 - Soy allergy
 - Other
 - None
9. Would you like to join the other participants for dinner on the evening of 28 October?
(RDMTraining4NFDI will cover up to 20€)
 - Yes
 - No
10. Do you have any questions or comments about this event? [Open answer]
11. I hereby expressly agree to the Data protection information RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Event: Research Data Management for NFDI Consortia (see right below)
 - Yes

Data protection information RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Event: Research Data Management for NFDI Consortia

Registration data (name, email address) of the participants will only be collected by us for the purpose of organising the event. The purpose of this data is to confirm the registration and to enable contact with the participants. It will not be passed on to third parties. For this purpose, personal data is collected in accordance with Art. 6 GDPR para. 1 (b).

Purpose and data categories

Personal data may be collected for the preparation, realisation, follow-up and documentation of events. This data includes a maximum of:

- Master data (name, title, form of address, function, etc.)
- Contact data (postal addresses, email, telephone, etc.)
- Event information
- Contact from ZB MED

Legal basis

For the purpose of preparing and organising an event and its documentation, the above-mentioned data is processed on the basis of your binding registration (Art. 6 para. 1 lit. b GDPR). For the purpose of event follow-up, e.g. for evaluations or reference to thematically similar follow-up events and publications relevant to the event, the above-mentioned data is stored on the basis of our legitimate interest (Art. 6 para. 1 lit. f GDPR) in improving the quality of our events.

Storage period

By registering, you consent to us contacting you and storing your data for the preparation, realisation, follow-up and documentation of the event. If there is no further contact with ZB MED, the personal data will be deleted from the database after 36 months with a reasonable processing period of up to three months and in individual cases after verification. In accordance with legal requirements, event documents are stored for at least ten years.

Your rights

You have the right to access and rectify the above-mentioned data categories. You can object to the processing of data for the purpose of event follow-up at any time.

Contact

If you have any questions or suggestions before or after the event, please email us at rdmtraining4nfdi-orga@lists.nfdi.de.